

Journals in the field “Language and Literature” indexed in Web of Science and Scopus databases. Verification of results of the scientific research in publishing technique

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Abstract

The paper analyses the publication of articles in scientific journals indexed in the world databases WoS and Scopus. It refers about high prices set by publishers that authors have to pay for publishing of scientific texts. Bibliometric indicators (JIF, SNIP) divide journals into quartiles. Publishing in scientific journals has detected enormous growth. We are talking about the massive publishing industry.

Key words: Journal articles, Data publishing techniques, Linguistics, Languages, Science evaluation, Bibliometrics, Web of science, Scopus, Journal citation reports, SCImago, Verification, Technical editors

Introduction

The data from the consulting firm Outsell in Burlingame, California, suggest that the science-publishing industry generated \$9.4 billion in revenue in 2011 and published around 1.8 million English-language articles – an average revenue per article of roughly \$5,000. Analysts estimate profit margins at 20-30% for the industry, so the average cost to the publisher for producing an article is likely to be around \$3,500-4,000 (1. pct. The cost of publishing).

Until recently, scientists have been sending the printed manuscripts of articles to publishers. The development of the Internet and electronic media began to gradually change the situation on the market regarding publishing and it turned in a direction of the detriment of the authors. This has led to increase publishing activities and a large number of scientific contributions that have been stepped up by modern editorial

systems and scientific communities such as Turkey, India, China, Mexico, Brazil, the Russian Federation and Iran.

The surplus of the offer on the market has aggravated the quality of review procedures, as it is increasingly difficult for publishers to get up for high-grade reviewers' reports. For time reasons, most of the reviews for PhD students are rejected. This situation is getting worse. Even 15 years ago, the review procedures made to guarantee the quality of publishing were very useful. Today, the share of good review reports has fallen below 20 percent. The situation is solved by the way that publishers refuse to accept manuscripts without a review report, or the review process is carried out by members of editorial boards. The reviews are based on the subjective opinions of the editors, but they must adhere to its scope a malpractice statement, therefore they are not so subjective.

The reaction of the system to a large surplus of manuscripts is the emergence of new titles of electronic journals. Since there is currently open free access, publishers have to choose an efficient funding model, and select readers and libraries whereby the contributors themselves, are no longer paying for their published posts. Prices move from a few hundred to thousand dollars. The prices of new published articles for authors move from 1,350 to 5,000 USD. The proportion of publishing in printed journals is decreasing, as well as the impact values of these periodicals. The share of published articles in printed periodicals has fallen as well as the citing – Impact Factor. The electronic versions have helped to increase the citing and Impact Factor. Even a large number of new journals are not sufficiently covered in order to satisfy the supply of all scientific articles. Due to the astronomical increase in publishing fees, a large number of predatory periodicals emerged and offered lower prices for published contributions. A large number of contributions sent out excludes the objectivity of review in editorial offices, and it happens that a contribution of high scientific value is not published. For the novice author, this experience is depressing.

Today there are two funding models for publishing: a traditional one in which the fee for the contribution is partially projected into a subscription and a new model in which the full article fee is paid by the author of the article itself. The majority of scientific journals, both print and electronic, are indexed in the two of the world's largest databases of ISI Web of Knowledge and Scopus.

The ISI Web of Knowledge database indexes 12.062 titles of journals in 2017 (1.094 titles with Open Access), of which 3.233 titles are social sciences, which is about 30 percent of the total number of indexed titles. The European database Scopus indexes a total of 28.606 periodical titles in 2017 (3,772 titles with Open Access) of which 12,346 titles of periodicals refer to social sciences. More than 65 percent of Scopus journals belong to journals in the natural field of science.

In the database ISI Web of Knowledge, the section of linguistics contains a total of 180 indexed titles of the world's top linguistic periodicals, out of which 4 titles are Open Access journals. The order of the first 10 rated journal titles indexed by the Journal Impact Factor (JIF) is shown pct. 2

Journals are divided into four quartiles in all the leading categories (pct. 1). For accreditation purposes, it is important to publish contributions that are in the first and second quartiles. In the first quartile (year 2016) of science field of linguistics in database Web of Science are classified 45 periodicals which have a bibliometric value Impact Factor from 3,593 to 1,241. The number of titles of journals by country of edition: USA 26 titles, England 16 titles, Netherland 2 titles and New Zealand 1 title. In the second quartile of science field of linguistics, are classified 45 titles of periodicals is have a bibliometric value Impact Factor from 1,214 to 0,667. The number of titles of journals by country of edition: England 21 titles, Netherland 11 titles, USA 8 titles, Germany 4 titles and Belgium 1 title.

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<input type="checkbox"/>	2 JOURNAL OF MEMORY AND LANGUAGE	8,541	3.065	0.00923
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 Bilingualism-Language and Cognition	2,210	3.010	0.00437
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 JOURNAL OF FLUENCY DISORDERS	968	2.714	0.00101
<input type="checkbox"/>	5 COMPUTATIONAL LINGUISTICS	2,235	2.528	0.00216
<input type="checkbox"/>	6 BRAIN AND LANGUAGE	6,186	2.439	0.00971
<input type="checkbox"/>	7 ReCALL	595	2.333	0.00081
<input type="checkbox"/>	8 LANGUAGE LEARNING & TECHNOLOGY	1,189	2.293	0.00115
<input type="checkbox"/>	9 INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE & COMMUNICATION DISORDERS	1,745	2.195	0.00321
<input type="checkbox"/>	10 COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS	1,010	2.135	0.00141

The second major source of indexed periodicals in the field of language and linguistics is the Elsevier-Scopus database (2. pct.).

The database Scopus indexes 12,346 periodical titles from the field of social sciences. Language and Linguistics has 720 titles, out of which 104 titles are Open Access journals. In the first quartile, there are 4 titles of journals and the second quartile contains 37 titles of journals with access to full texts.

The Scopus database also has journals divided into four quartiles. The quartiles of the journals are counted under SCImago Journal Ranking (SJR). The SJR indicates the citation rate for the titles of the journals for the previous three-year period. The highest value of the SJR is the US Journal of Memory and Language with SJR 3.403. For 153 titles of journals in the field of language and linguistics, the SJR value in the first quartile is from 3.403 to 0.346. Distribution of journal titles by country of publication: England 72 titles; USA 39 titles; Netherlands 22 titles; Germany 11 titles; Australia and Belgium 2 titles; Malaysia, Spain, Switzerland, Hungary and France have 1 journal title.

In the second quartile, there are 152 period titles and the SJR is in the range from 0.341 to 0.133. Distribution of journal titles by country of publication: Netherlands 31 titles; England 27 titles; USA 18 titles; Germany 13 titles; Spain 9 titles; Belgium 6 titles; Australia 5 titles; Estonia 4 titles; Canada, Poland, Hungary, Italy, France 3 titles; Chile, Slovenia, Brazil, Denmark, Finland, Malaysia 2 titles; Taiwan, South Africa, South Korea, New Zealand, the Russian Federation, Slovakia, Azerbaijan, the Philippines, the Czech Republic, Singapore, Switzerland and Norway have one title.

All subject areas		Language and Linguistics		All regions / countries		All types		2015		
<input type="checkbox"/> Display only Open Access Journals	<input type="checkbox"/> Display only ScIeLO Journals (In Progress)	Display journals with at least 0		Citable Docs. (3years)		Apply		Download data		
1 - 50 of 631										
Title	Type	↓ SJR	H index	Total Docs. (2015)	Total Docs. (3years)	Total Refs.	Total Cites (3years)	Citable Docs. (3years)	Cites / Doc. (2years)	Ref. / Doc.
1 Journal of Memory and Language	journal	3.403 Q1	109	59	215	3820	916	199	5.35	64.75
2 Journal of Communication	journal	3.327 Q1	82	68	194	2936	846	186	3.03	43.18
3 Cognition	journal	2.770 Q1	142	218	513	11175	1888	498	3.45	51.26
4 Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience	journal	2.712 Q1	171	162	602	10036	2226	596	3.46	61.95
5 Communication Theory	journal	2.620 Q1	53	39	69	1614	186	66	2.87	41.38
6 Studies in Second Language Acquisition	journal	2.486 Q1	34	27	97	829	185	91	1.58	30.70
7 Language Learning	journal	2.473 Q1	62	50	186	2513	373	141	2.10	50.26
8 Artificial Intelligence	journal	2.426 Q1	115	90	187	3944	892	179	4.50	43.82
9 Linguistic Inquiry	journal	2.255 Q1	52	21	78	1267	117	77	1.41	60.33
10 Journal of Experimental Psychology: Learning, Memory and Cognition	journal	2.226 Q1	121	230	438	5895	1133	422	2.49	25.63

Price policy of journals on a language-and-linguistics topic

An important publisher for the field of language and linguistics is Elsevier which contains 32 titles of periodicals. The portal website of this publisher allows automatic manuscript insertion and tracking reviews after registration. It contains guidelines for authors, basic information indexed titles, electronic ordering, key bibliometrics indexes of journals. Publishing fees for Elsevier are approximately \$ 1,100 USD. Elsevier publishes some titles of magazines in which posts are published by the authors free of fees. Other major publishers of language and linguistics periodical is Wiley Blackwell, which has 45 journals titles. The prices for publishing are from 1,500 to 4,000 USD. Successful publisher of linguistic periodicals with 22 titles is the British publisher Cambridge University Press which has a user manual with the possibility of automated entry and tracking of contributions. Publishing fees (printing rate, metadata, citation links, permanent worldwide access to full text, online access, and database indexing) are 1,675 USD. Another major publisher of scientific journals is SAGE Publishing from the USA which has more than 1,000 titles of periodicals from 400 world institutions, from this 19 titles of journals have a field of language and linguistics. The worth for publishing of an article is 3,000 USD. The Oxford University Press publishes over 300 journals titles. 19 titles of journals are from language and linguistics. This publisher produces top-quality journals from current research of the scientific community. In majority, the publishing fee for this publisher is situated between 1,128 to 2,820 USD. The Springer publishes 80 journals in a common field of education and language. It is a global publisher for the academic sphere and supports publishing of hybrid journals and open-access journals. The Kluwer Academic Publisher was joined with BioMed Central, Palgrave Macmillan and Nature Research due to some economic reasons. The author pays 3,000 USD for the printout of the contribution. The successful publisher is British Routledge, which is

a member of Taylor & Francis with 1.800 journals titles, 131 titles focus on language and literature. The author pays for publication 2,950 USD including tax.

Conclusion

Currently, there is a large number of scientific journals from the area of language and linguistics and literature that are indexed in the Web of Science and Scopus databases. Publishing in these resources is one of the basic conditions for the accreditation criteria and professional growth of scientific and pedagogical staff in Slovakia. Low financial rating and low project availability are limiting factors for Slovak researchers and restrict publishing in prestigious titles of foreign periodicals.

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